

REVISITING DRUG -INDUCED LIVER INJURY***Sahar Youssef**

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ABSTRACT

Liver is a primary organ in the human body responsible for numerous physiological function such as bile production, detoxification, fat soluble vitamin storage, drug and bilirubin metabolism, immunity, and digestion. The safety of drug usage is generally concerned, and significant improvement is being made in our understanding of drug induced liver injury (DILI) via human and animal research. This review is to revisit certain common drugs induced adverse effects to liver with an overview of promising future of DILI research.

KEYWORDS: Liver, Orlistat, Statins, Paracetamol, NSAIDs, Formaldehyde, In Vitro Models.

INTRODUCTION

The liver is an essential organ and has several functions such as metabolism of the body, bile secretion, synthesis of plasma protein, production of hormone, vitamin storage and removal of toxic substances. The liver is susceptible to the toxicity from the agent such as drugs.^[1] Certain drugs have the possible to injure the liver when taken in an excess or when administered within normal therapeutic dose.^[2,3] Different susceptibility to drugs between people due to genetic or environmental factors are reported. Environmental factors such as age, gender, nutritional status, drug-drug interaction, drug adverse reactions, alcohol consumption, pregnancy, inflammation, and diseases such as HIV, and hepatitis. Drug induced liver injury may proceed to liver fibrosis, liver failure and even death.^[4] The mechanisms for drug induced liver injury might be due to mitochondria membrane breakdown, elevated oxidative stress, increased apoptosis, necrosis,

and organ damages.^[5,6] Necrosis pathway is initiated by mitochondrial permeability transition and results in cell swelling, loss of plasma membrane integrity and eventually cell death.^[7,8] Hepatocyte apoptosis is an essential moderator of liver injury.^[9] Significantly, apoptosis can occur via the extrinsic pathway activated by the stimulation of death receptors, such as tumor necrosis factor-related apoptosis-inducing ligand (TRAIL), Fas, tumor necrosis factor receptor 1 (TNFR1), intrinsic mitochondrial pathway activated by intracellular perturbations, such as lysosomal permeabilization, DNA injury, endoplasmic reticulum stress, oxidative damage, and increased levels of calcium. Other types of liver injury caused by many factors such as alcohol consumption, viral hepatitis, non-alcoholic fatty liver disease, autoimmune hepatitis, and cholestatic liver disease.^[10]

Orlistat

Orlistat is considered as an anti-obesity drug, inhibits gastric lipase, which diminishes the absorption of dietary fats, activates weight reduction, and reducing diabetes progression among high-risk patients.^[11] Orlistat therapy limitations were observed, and some patients are sustained to achieve weight loss after one year of treatment. Moreover, the gastrointestinal adverse effect of orlistat as steatorrhea due to impaired absorption of dietary fat, abdominal pain, diarrhea, lead to the presence of undigested lipids in the intestinal tract and adversely affect the quality of life of patients.^[12] Caution is advised when recommending orlistat to patients with obstructed bile ducts and abnormal liver function tests.^[13] Liver injury is a documented side effect of orlistat in animals. using electron microscopy to study the effect of orlistat on the liver of adult male albino rats at a dose of 32 mg/kg/day for two weeks. Some hepatocyte cells showed irregular shaped nuclei and chromatin condensation, others with pyknotic nuclei, vacuolated cytoplasm, swollen mitochondria and dilated rough endoplasmic reticulum. The endoplasmic reticulum act as a site of radical production and its membrane is rich in polyunsaturated fatty acids which are vulnerable to free radical attack. and the deteriorating changes in the endoplasmic reticulum could be due to raised oxidative stress.^[14]

Statins

Statins are 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl-Coenzyme A (HMG-CoA) reductase inhibitors.^[15] They are used for lipid-lowering and for treatment of cardiovascular and cerebrovascular diseases.^[16] The commonly used statin drugs in clinical practice including atorvastatin, fluvastatin, lovastatin, pitavastatin, pravastatin, rosuvastatin, and simvastatin. Statin caused liver injury displaying in either hepatocellular or cholestatic patterns.^[17] Atorvastatin is

widely used in the clinical practice such as lipid lowering medications, improving endothelial function, reducing oxidative stress, and adjusting inflammatory processes.^[18] Hepatotoxicity associated with statins therapy has become one of the clinical concerns that require sufficient interest. A comprehensive and detailed analysis of the hepatotoxicity of statins based on the data of the US Food and Drug Administration suggested that atorvastatin had the most significant signal strength in cholestatic pruritus. Fluvastatin displayed a significant signal strength in autoimmune hepatitis. In rats, Liver sections of Atorvastatin group received 80 mg/kg/day orally for four weeks showed dilated congested blood liver sinusoids and focal cellular infiltrations.^[19]

Paracetamol

Paracetamol or acetaminophen (APAP) is widely used as drug of choice for acute and chronic pain^[20] Excessive APAP metabolism depleted glutathione and raised N-acetyl-p-benzoquinoneimide (NAPQI) levels, resulting in oxidative stress, DNA damage, and cell necrosis in the liver, leads to liver damage.^[21] In rat, a therapeutic dose of paracetamol for 14 days causes significant changes in the liver. Hepatocytes showed marked vacuolar degeneration, vacuoles in cytoplasm, pyknotic nuclei, dilated central, portal veins and mononuclear cell infiltration. Moreover, increased collagen fibers, decreased PAS reaction and increased apoptotic cells.^[22] it has been displayed that APAP can induce endoplasmic reticulum stress and unfolded protein reactions which might lead to hepatic damage. In addition, autophagy induced by APAP in the mouse liver and primary cultured hepatocytes speed up APAP-induced liver cell death.^[23] Impairment of hepatic autophagy cause several harmful effects by preventing the removal of injured organelles and proteins, also it can activate the production of reactive oxygen species, which can further damage hepatocytes and or it can trigger inflammatory response in the liver which could cause many liver diseases.^[24,25]

Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory

The principal mechanism of action of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory (NSAIDs) is the inhibition of the enzyme cyclooxygenase (COX). Cyclooxygenase is necessary to convert arachidonic acid into thromboxane, prostaglandins, and prostacyclin. The commonly NSAIDs are naproxen, ibuprofen, indomethacin, diclofenac sodium, piroxicam, and celecoxib. NSAIDs should be used carefully in patients with liver dysfunction.^[26] NSAIDs including indomethacin are widely used as an anti-inflammatory and analgesic-antipyretic as

acute and chronic pain, rheumatoid arthritis, gout, degenerative joint diseases, and acute musculoskeletal disorders. However, degeneration, necrosis and erosion in many experimental animal species were reported and limited its usage. Mitochondrial damage and coagulative necrosis of the liver including DNA injury and elevation in oxidative stress are involved in the pathogenesis of indomethacin induced hepatotoxicity.^[27] Diclofenac sodium is one of the NSAIDs most linked to adverse effect of hepatocellular and renal damage. Diclofenac sodium damages hepatic and renal tissues by increasing malondialdehyde and decreasing glutathione in hepatic tissues. This oxidative stress leads to the secretion of cytochrome c, which triggers the caspase cascade and causes hepatocytes to undergo apoptosis.^[28]

Formaldehyde

Formaldehyde (FA) is commonly toxicant used in many cosmetics, pharmaceutical products, textiles, preservatives, and agriculture industries, but presents substantial health risks. It is used for cadaver embalming, fixation for organs and tissues, disinfection, and sterilization techniques. Formaldehyde hepatotoxicity occurs through inhalation, ingestion, or injection. Recent investigations showed acute FA poisoning leads to hepatotoxicity and its toxicity is related to oxidative stress, inflammatory reaction, and ferroptosis.^[29] Rats received 2ml of 0.1% of formaldehyde showed a significant increase in the plasma level of SGOT and SGPT.^[30]

Previous research suggested that adult male albino rats injected intraperitoneally with formaldehyde (10mg/kg BW) for ten days displayed an increase in the liver weights, congested dilated central, portal veins, blood sinusoids and increase in serum activities of ALT and AST.^[31,32]

Promising Future Using In Vitro Models Techniques

Three-dimensional (3D) or Two-dimensional (2D) cell models presently the most used tools for initiating preclinical drugs and investigating the drug-specific hazards of DILI. HepaRG cell line was developed for toxicological studies, and when fully differentiated, they look like mature hepatocytes and maintain typical liver function. Few technical problems face HepaRG cell line investigations but it is useful for in vitro studies of targeted drugs in cholestasis and steatosis. In vitro models of primary human hepatocytes (PHHs) which are considered the gold standard for assessing liver drug toxicity but faces challenges and few limitations in restricted availability because this dependent on rare organ donations and patient biopsies.

Hepatocyte-like cells derived from induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) are also used and several studies to resolve any practical problems or highest prices of commercial product which delays widespread application. In vitro models can be improved through developing co-cultures composed of liver parenchymal and non-parenchymal cells that simulate the liver in vivo condition.^[33] Indeed, In vitro models represent an important opportunity to better understand liver response to drug injury and their mechanism.^[34]

CONCLUSION

Drug -induced liver injury is the primary cause of acute liver failure and one of the most important reasons for drug withdrawal from the pharmaceutical companies and marketplace. Human and animal research are very useful to predict, optimize dose, and duration of using drugs. Moreover, studying and comparisons of data research allowed understanding the potential mechanism of drug induced hepatotoxicity. Importantly, to apply the study results in human body, more confirmation research is necessary to confirm the results detected in animal research. Significantly, further innovative in vitro model investigations should be improved to understand cellular processes underlying adverse consequences to those compounds and choosing safer and cheaper molecules for pre-clinical assessments and trials.

REFERENCES

1. Sahu CR. Mechanisms Involved in Toxicity of Liver Caused by Piroxicam in Mice and Protective Effects of Leaf Extract of Hibiscus rosa-sinensis L. Clin Med Insights Arthritis Musculoskelet Disord, 2016 Jan 19; 9: 9-13. doi: 10.4137/CMAMD.S29463. PMID: 26819562; PMCID: PMC4720181.
2. Roy, S., Shah, Z. & Chakraborty, G.S. A brief overview of drug-induced liver damage. Egypt J Intern Med., 2024; 36: 56. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43162-024-00315-7>
3. Suh JI. Drug-induced liver injury. J Yeungnam Med Sci., 2020; 37(1): 2-12.
4. Zhou, Y., Wang, J., Zhang, D. *et al.* Mechanism of drug-induced liver injury and hepatoprotective effects of natural drugs. *Chin Med.*, 2021; 16: 135. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13020-021-00543-x>
5. Allison, R., Guraka, A., Shawa, I. T., Tripathi, G., Moritz, W., & Kermanizadeh, A. Drug induced liver injury – a 2023 update. Journal of Toxicology and Environmental Health, Part B, 2023; 26(8): 442–467. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10937404.2023.2261848>

6. Garcia-Cortes, M., M. Robles-Diaz, C. Stephens, A. Ortega-Alonso, I. Lucena, and R. Andrade. Drug induced liver injury: An update. *Arch. Toxicol.*, 2020; 94(10): 3381–407. doi:10.1007/s00204-020-02885-1.
7. Mihajlovic, M., & Vinken, M. Mitochondria as the Target of Hepatotoxicity and Drug-Induced Liver Injury: Molecular Mechanisms and Detection Methods. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 2022; 23(6): 3315. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms23063315>
8. Shojaie, L., A. Iorga, and L. Dara. Cell death in liver diseases: A review. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.*, 2020; 21(24): 9682. doi:10.3390/ijms21249682.
9. Sefa Kucukler, Ekrem Darendelioğlu, Cuneyt Caglayan, Adnan Ayna, Serkan Yıldırım, Fatih Mehmet Kandemir, Zingerone attenuates vancomycin-induced hepatotoxicity in rats through regulation of oxidative stress, inflammation and apoptosis, *Life Sciences*, 2020; 10: 1016/j.lfs.2020.118382, 259, (118382)
10. Y. Zhang, Y. Lu, H. Ji, *et al.* Anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidative stress and novel therapeutic targets for cholestatic liver injury *Biosci. Trends*, 2019; 13(1): 23-31, 10.5582/bst.2018.01247
11. Escobedo-Moratilla, A.; Patiño-Rodríguez, O.; Arzola-Paniagua, A.; Herrera, J.L.; Senosiain, J.P.; Pérez-Urizar, J. Biological Activity of Resveratrol, a Plant-Derived Polyphenol, in Combination with Orlistat: A Preclinical Study on Anti-Obesity Effects. *Appl. Sci.*, 2025; 15: 9533. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app15179533>
12. Uuh Narvaez JJ, Chan Zapata I, Segura Campos MR. Combined Potential of Orlistat with Natural Sources and Their Bioactive Compounds Against Obesity: A Review. *Molecules*, 2025 May 30; 30(11): 2392. doi: 10.3390/molecules30112392. PMID: 40509279; PMCID: PMC12156891.
13. Bansal AB, Patel P, Al Khalili Y. Orlistat. In: *StatPearls* [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing, 2025; from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK542202/>
14. Youssef, S. Light and Electron Microscopic Study of the Effect of Orlistat on the Liver of Adult Male Albino Rats and the Possible Protective Role of β -Carotene. *Forensic Medicine and Anatomy Research*, 2018; 6: 20-36. doi: 10.4236/fmar.2018.62003.
15. Wang L, Wang Y. Statin therapy and mortality in critically ill heart failure patients: Insights from a triangulated real-world design study. *PLoS One.*, 2025 Oct 17; 20(10): e0334822. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0334822. PMID: 41105670; PMCID: PMC12533876.
16. Ma MM, Xu YY, Sun LH, Cui WJ, Fan M, Zhang S, Liu L, Wu LZ, Li LC. Statin-Associated Liver Dysfunction and Muscle Injury: epidemiology, Mechanisms, and

- Management Strategies. *Int J Gen Med.*, 2024; 17: 2055-2063
<https://doi.org/10.2147/IJGM.S460305>
17. Averbukh LD, Turshudzhyan A, Wu DC, Wu GY. Statin-induced Liver Injury Patterns: A Clinical Review. *J Clin Transl Hepatol*, 2022 Jun 28; 10(3): 543-552. doi: 10.14218/JCTH.2021.00271. Epub 2022 Jan 10. PMID: 35836753; PMCID: PMC9240239.
18. Liu, J.-C., Lei, S.-Y., Zhang, D.-H., He, Q. Y., Sun, Y. Y., Zhu, H. J., et al. The pleiotropic effects of statins: a comprehensive exploration of neurovascular unit modulation and blood–brain barrier protection. *Mol. Med.*, 2024; 30(1): 256. doi:10.1186/s10020-024-01025-0.
19. Youssef, S. IMPACT OF L-CARNITINE ON ATORVASTATIN INDUCED LIVER, TESTES AND GASTRIC INJURY IN RATS. *World journal of pharmaceutical research*, 2020; 9(8): 86-100.
20. Gonçalves, A.C.; Coelho, A.M.; da Cruz Castro, M.L.; Pereira, R.R.; da Silva Araújo, N.P.; Ferreira, F.M.; Machado Júnior, P.A.; Pio, S.; Vital, C.E.; Bezerra, F.S.; et al. Modulation of Paracetamol-Induced Hepatotoxicity by Acute and Chronic Ethanol Consumption in Mice: A Study Pilot. *Toxics*, 2024; 12; 857. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxics12120857>
21. Chidiac, A. S., Buckley, N. A., Noghrehchi, F., & Cairns, R. Paracetamol (acetaminophen) overdose and hepatotoxicity: mechanism, treatment, prevention measures, and estimates of burden of disease. *Expert Opinion on Drug Metabolism & Toxicology*, 2023; 19(5): 297–317. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17425255.2023.2223959>
22. Eisa, Samaa; Youssef, Sahar; and Abd Elshafy, Shadia "Effect of Paracetamol on the liver of Adult Male Albino Rats and the Possible Protective effect of Folic Acid," *Al-Azhar International Medical Journal*: 2024; 5(11): Article 9. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.58675/2682-339X.2740>
23. Jieyu Yang, Zhaoming Chen, Yuexia Yang, Bingbing Zheng, Yu Zhu, Fapu Wu, Hu Xiong, Visualization of Endogenous Hypochlorite in Drug-Induced Liver Injury Mice via a Bioluminescent Probe Combined with Firefly Luciferase mRNA-Loaded Lipid Nanoparticles, *Analytical Chemistry*, 2024; 10: 1021/acs.analchem.4c00008, 96, 18, (6978-6985),
24. Cai X, Hua S, Deng J, Du Z, Zhang D, Liu Z et al Astaxanthin activated the Nrf2/HO-1 pathway to enhance autophagy and inhibit ferroptosis, ameliorating acetaminophen-induced liver injury. *ACS Appl Mater Interfaces*, 2022; 14: 42887–42903.

25. Saleh, A.K., El-Masry, T.A., El-Kadem, A.H. et al. Exploring drug-induced liver injury: comprehensive insights into mechanisms and management of hepatotoxic agents. *Futur J Pharm Sci.*, 2025; 11: 38, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43094-025-00788-5>
26. Ghlichloo I, Gerriets V. Nonsteroidal Anti-Inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs) [Updated 2023 May 1]. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025 Jan. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK547742/>
27. Sheeba Khan a, Faiz Noor Khan Yusufi b, Ahad Noor Khan Yusufi .Comparative effect of indomethacin (IndoM) on the enzymes of carbohydrate metabolism, brush border membrane and oxidative stress in the kidney, small intestine and liver of rats. *Toxicology Reports*, 2019; 6: 389-394
28. Khalil, E., Fahmy EL-baroudy, N., Mahgoub, L., & Nageeb, M. An Insight about Diclofenac induced hepato-renal toxicity: A Review Article. *Zagazig University Medical Journal*, 2025; 31(1.1): 56-61. doi: 10.21608/zumj.2024.277963.3265
29. Paudel S, Sim H, Kang E, Kim M et al., Characterization of formaldehyde-induced hepatotoxicity based on proteometabolomic analysis *Toxicology Letters*, 2025; 412: 212-222
30. Ahmed, A., & Awad, M. The effect of Melatonin Hormone on Formaldehyde-Induced Liver Injury in adult male albino rats: A Light and electron Microscopic Study. *The Egyptian Journal of Anatomy*, 2017; 40(2): 323-335. doi: 10.21608/EJANA.2018.16909
31. Mahmoud, S., Hegab, A., Ibrahim, I., & Farag, A.). THE EFFECT OF FORMALDEHYDE ON THE LIVER OF ADULT MALE ALBINO RATS AND POSSIBLE PROTECTIVE ROLE OF VITAMIN C. *Egyptian Society of Clinical Toxicology Journal*, 2016; 4(1): 1-22. doi: 10.21608/esctj.2016.66129
32. Youssef S and Shehata N (2010) Protective Effects of Panax Ginseng Against Formaldehyde Induced Hepatotoxicity in Male Adults Albino Rats: histopathological and Immunohistochemical Studies 14 Science. Congress Faculty. Veterinary Medical Assiut University Egypt.
33. Guo, K., van den Beucken, T. Advances in drug-induced liver injury research: in vitro models, mechanisms, omics and gene modulation techniques. *Cell Biosci.*, 2024; 14: 134. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13578-024-01317-2>
34. Collins SD, Yuen G, Tu T, et al. In Vitro Models of the Liver: Disease Modeling, Drug Discovery and Clinical Applications. In: Tirnitz-Parker JEE, editor. Hepatocellular Carcinoma [Internet]. Brisbane (AU): Codon Publications, 2019 Oct 24; Chapter 3.

Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK549191/> doi:
10.15586/hepatocellularcarcinoma.2019.ch3